

"BUSINESS IN SOCIETY: MEASURING IMPACT AND CREATING CHANGE"

18th ABIS Annual Colloquium | 29-30 October, ESMT Berlin

On October 29 - 30, 2019, in the light of the 30th anniversary of the fall of the Berlin Wall and the 18 years since the foundation of ABIS - The Academy of Business in Society, we organised our 18th Annual Colloquium. We were invited by our long-term member ESMT Berlin to their historic main building in Berlin, which formerly housed the State Council of the East Germany.

85 participants representing **50 organisations** from **20+ countries** joined us to discuss "Business in Society: Measuring Impact and Creating Change". We offered a platform for high level discussions with our business-academic network on the importance of measuring impact, the challenges that academia and business are facing to maximize their impact and for sharing best practices that create positive change for reaching the SDGs.

Here is how you can re-live the highlights of our Colloquium (or catch what you missed!):

- Read this report, which includes sessions' summaries, impressions, interviews and more
- Some of our speakers have made their presentations available: you can find them [HERE](#)
- Take a look at the photos below and on our website
- Watch our official after-movie and talking head interviews released in the report
- Check our related projects and initiatives on our website (for example, our Scenario Exploration System Workshops)
- Share this report, post pictures or videos on your social media with the hashtag #ABISIMPACT and don't forget to tag us @abisglobal

[Our website](#)

DAY 1: 29 OCTOBER 2019

The first day of our Colloquium was opened by **Yury Blagov**, Director of the PwC Center for CSR at **St. Petersburg University**. He is also the newly appointed ABIS Board Member. He highlighted that the traditional Business in Society paradigm is changing in the era of UN SDGs. Companies are transforming themselves from a commonly shared and established model towards a more advanced "corporate sustainability", not only searching for immediate "win-win" solutions, but aiming to achieve truly shared triple bottom line value creation. In this process, they are engaging and collaborating with different stakeholders, including academia.

"ACADEMICS FOCUS TOO MUCH ON DEFINITIONS AND THEORETICAL CONCEPTS. THIS IS WHY IT IS DIFFICULT TO MOVE FORWARD"

PANEL DISCUSSION: THE ROLE OF BUSINESS IN SOCIETY - TRENDS AND ACADEMIC INSIGHTS

We were pleased to welcome our Steering Committee members: **Joanna Radeke**, Manager at Center for Sustainable Business and Leadership, **ESMT Berlin**; **Thomas Osburg**, Dean of Studies 'Automotive & Mobility Management Head of Competence Center Entrepreneurship, **Fresenius University of Applied Sciences**; **Yury Blagov**, Director of the PwC Center for CSR at **St. Petersburg University** and **Boleslaw Rok**, Professor, **Kozminski University** at the introductory panel.

The panel reflected on the developments of corporate responsibility from “nice to have” to strategic and operational integration and business action towards the SDGs. The discussions steered towards drivers of advancing sustainable development, but also the challenges that businesses and academia are facing. One of the main challenges remains impact measurement and with that the lack and quality of data and different frameworks and approaches.

All of the speakers agreed that academia and business need to work closely together to overcome barriers and to accomplish the comprehensive sustainability goals in a way that will ensure translation of the latest knowledge in a relevant and applicable manner into impactful innovation.

RESEARCH PRESENTATIONS

We were thrilled that so many authors responded to our Call for Papers and presented their research during the first day of our Colloquium in three tracks:

- **Assessing and Measuring Business Impact**
- **Drivers and barriers to sustainability and SDG implementation**
- **New approaches to sustainable value creation**

In each track, we had the pleasure to get an overview on 5 - 6 research papers. You have the possibility to find short descriptions on each in the following slides.

TRACK 1: ASSESSING AND MEASURING BUSINESS IMPACT

CHAIR: IVO MATSER - CEO, ABIS

Francesco Perrini, Bocconi University: A systematic literature review of social value metrics. Measuring the societal impact of social enterprises and the advantages of SROI

Societal impact is a concept with many possible definitions and there are up to 180 different methods and tools available for making a social impact measurement. The research consists of a systematic review to see what tools are mostly used by companies and how many of these are cited by the literature. Main outcomes that emerged from the review is that there is a huge fragmentation of the existing literature on social impact. Moreover, The SROI seems to be the most popular method to measure social impact. The third result is describing how impact measurement is undertaken by social enterprises.

Ephaim Daka, Turku School of Economics: Impact investments and the emerging climate markets: a social benefit perspective

Wood burning is a big contributor to climate change, and 31% is done in Africa. This causes forest depletion and contributes to climate change. Clean technology is a very important because it counteracts deforestation and contributes to many sustainable development goals as clean energy or climate change mitigation. The research questions that were proposed are (1) how Cleantech brings positive impact to people affected by global climate problems and (2) what criteria can be used to promote investments. The findings from the literature review show that impact investments into cleantech companies have not shown real benefit in the case of Sub-Saharan Africa.

Yanina Kowszyk, University of Barcelona - Social impact evaluations in the private sector: capacity building challenges in Latin America

The paper aims to describe the interest, knowledge and methods for evaluating CSR programs in the Latin American business sector and provides empirical evidence to understand the current situation and main obstacles to advance the practice of impact evaluations of CSR activities. The literature review shows how there is a relevant interest and knowledge of CSR programs and the presence of effective impact evaluations among companies. A survey among CEOs was conducted and the results show lack of information on how to measure CSR and its challenges. Confusion also arises between concepts and methodologies of measurements. The survey indicated that CEOs know what social impact and its implications mean, however not how to methodologically measure it. There is a need to adjust expectations of companies, understand benefits, when to make impact assessment, how to prepare evaluation budgets, and to find out better ways to use the results.

Anastasia Petrova-Savchenko, St. Petersburg University - Measuring Corporate Impact in Pursuit of UN Sustainable Development Goals: Main Challenges

This research aims to shed light on how corporations deal with the SDGs in Russia. A survey was conducted among corporations to see if there an integration of the SDG within their activities. The research then combines quantitative and qualitative data, questionnaires and non-financial reports and analysis. The results show that the most popular SDGs are good health and well being (SDG 3), responsible consumption and production (SDG 12), and partnerships for the goals (SDG 17). 75% of companies integrate SDGs but only 64% of companies measure the impact of the SDGs in short-term and only one single company measures SDGs in long-term perspectives. The biggest challenge to measure seems to be the lack of motivation for companies due to weak stakeholders request.

Michel Kalika, EFMD - Measuring Business Impact: Lessons from the business schools

The main question addressed in the case study was how to extract the experience of business recommendations to business schools. BSIS – business school impact system, a mainstream method to measure impact of business schools was described in detail. The method focuses on 7 specific impact dimensions - financial impact, educational impact, business development impact, intellectual impact, impact within regional ecosystem, societal impact and image impact. To build trust, to improve accountability and to build positive image of business schools 10 questions are proposed to be filled out to better clarify positive impact. Both academia and business answered that they need to measure impact because of pressure from stakeholders and they need to improve their communication to them.

Wayne Visser, Antwerp Management School - Measuring Future Resilience: A Multi-Level Index

Resilience is ability to survive to disruption, it is the capacity of individuals and groups (like families, communities, organizations, cities, societies, or nature) to cope effectively with the impact of major, rapid changes (like disasters, crises or emergencies) and to return to a healthy state afterwards. There are many levels of resilience, as socio-ecological resilience, organizational resilience or individual resilience. The main question addressed in the paper was: "What are the essential characteristics of resilient living systems?" There is a need to rethink systems to build on this resilience. The research proposed to consider five pathways to resilience: secure, smart, shared, sustainable and satisfying, each with different measurement component. For each component, a set of questions were created that were disseminated to employees, organizations and to individuals in a form of a questionnaire.

TRACK 2: DRIVERS AND BARRIERS TO SUSTAINABILITY AND SDG IMPLEMENTATION

CHAIR: LIN LERPOLD - ASSOCIATE PROFESSOR, STOCKHOLM SCHOOL OF ECONOMICS

Dmitri Knatko, St. Petersburg State University - Integrating sustainable supply chain under institutional voids: extending the impact of focal company

The objective of the research was to find antecedents and drivers of adoption (integration) of sustainable supply chain management in Russia using the sample of large corporations Gazprom, Rosneft, SIBUR, Lukoil and Nornickel. The research combined primary data from face-to-face interviews with companies' representatives and secondary sources of data and applied triangulation procedure to obtain reliable results. The research shows that only one company implemented sustainable goals into strategic plans with triple bottom KPIs. The reason why majority of companies who already adopted sustainable practices from developed countries is that the learning activities that precede adoption of sustainability rely heavily on many collaborative, integrative and innovative actions that are harder to do in conditions of developing countries.

Erturk Ismail, Alliance Manchester Business School - Governance framework for sustainable finance: how to think beyond shareholder value maximization and search for high yield in the age of UN SDGs

The aim of the research was to problematise the sustainable finance practices and objectives against a background of the evolution of the corporate governance models that shape corporate behavior. There is a tendency in both policy and practice to discuss sustainable finance without explicit critical

engagement with the ongoing debates on the shareholder value-driven corporate governance model. The goal of the paper is to develop a theoretical framework to understand what analytical problems we face in developing a governance framework for effective sustainable finance practices. There is need to learn from post-crisis debates about knowledge problems in financial economics, culture in financial institutions and the consequences of shareholder value maximization. The sustainable finance agenda presents new challenges for business schools and financial institutions in creating a knowledge framework that is capable of producing techniques and evaluative models that lead to allocation of capital for a sustainable economy.

Joel Diener, Catholic University of Eichstaett-Ingolstadt - SRI and Non-Financial Impact: Putting the European Commission's Action Plan for Sustainable Finance into Perspective

Many millennium goals of United Nations were missed and without change sustainable development goals (SDGs) will not be met either. Increased investments only do not lead to similar sustainability achievements. The practitioners perspective is that investment institutions overestimate the significance of financial aspects and underrate the importance of ethical aspects for their customers. The outcome of the research showed that the role of fund management and shareholder engagement is undervalued in the European Commission action plan and needs to be addressed in more detail to unveil its full potential.

Jan Beyne, Antwerp Management School - Sustainability Review of companies in the Port of Antwerp

The research focused on assessing the nature and extent of attention to sustainability by Port community companies, getting in depth analysis of their reporting on sustainability. The goal was to analyze if SDG reporting is helping the trend towards integrated thinking about sustainability. The findings showed that most of the companies (68%) have no reporting on sustainability issues on their

website or in their annual reports, or they do not have any website. There is a need for increasing both awareness of and knowledge about the SDGs within companies. This need pertains to the overall SDG framework and the 2030 Agenda.

Yury E. Blagov, GSOM St. Petersburg State University: The development of Corporate Sustainability model for reaching SDGs: evidence from the «Report on Social Investments in Russia 2019»

The purpose of the research is to investigate the peculiarities of the search for a new model of Corporate Sustainability through the transformation of the Corporate Social Performance of leading Russian companies. These companies are not only searching for immediate “win-win” solutions, being prepared for achieving shared triple bottom line value creation, but also for “lose-win” ones in favour of sustainable development. The research is based on the empirical data from the 2014 and 2019 Reports on Social Investments in Russia. The data led to the conclusion that developments in Russian business is generally in line with the global trend of making Corporate Social Performance more strategic and oriented to value creation for business and society. Two thirds (75%) of the responding companies have implemented the principles of CSR and Sustainable Development into their business strategies. The “Corporate Sustainability 2.0” model is going to be predominant and supported by the “win-win” orientation of CSR strategies. The search for the “Corporate Sustainability 3.0” model is hampered by the relatively low level of cooperation for sustainable development at industry and cross-sector levels.

TRACK 3: NEW APPROACHES TO SUSTAINABLE VALUE CREATION

**CHAIR: THOMAS OSBURG - DEAN OF STUDIES & HEAD OF COMPETENCE CENTER
ENTREPRENEURSHIP, FRESENIUS UNIVERSITY OF APPLIED SCIENCES**

Eva Niesten, Alliance Manchester Business School - Collaborating for environmental sustainability: Environmental and economic value

The paper focuses on reviewing 121 articles on environmental inter-firm alliances that are emerging to create economic value by exploiting new market opportunities while simultaneously seeking to generate positive environmental impacts. Recent discussions on value creation in inter-firm alliances identify stakeholders beyond the boundaries of the alliance and thereby propose a new field of enquiry that revolves around the differences between internal value and external value, or externalities. In the paper two types of external motivation value were classified - environmental and knowledge value. The outcomes of paper showcases that economic value cannot only be generated internally, but also by internalizing externalities or in other words by creating economic value from environmental value.

Boleslaw Rok, Kozminski University - Positive impact entrepreneurship: examples from the start-up community in Poland

The main goal of the research was to identify potential drivers for innovative solutions in sustainable entrepreneurship – positive impact start-ups. The new model of entrepreneurship is focused on interactive process of crowdsourcing or stakeholder engagement with a view on the sustainability products and closing the loop in the material flow at the same time. Positive impact start-ups operating in different sectors in Poland were analysed and the strengths and weaknesses of their business models

Category of articles according to Gartner (1985)'s dimensions

3. Analysis of the results

- Synthesis of results
- Content analysis

for sustainability were identified by using semi-structured interviews within the case companies, document analysis and the direct observation and conversations with diverse stakeholders. The outcome of the paper implies that positive impact start-ups act as change agents as they develop sustainability as a purpose or internal motivation, integrate innovation for sustainability into business processes, and concentrate on improving impact on society.

Isabel Galvis, Turku School of Economics - Social entrepreneurs' attitudes towards growth and its role in shaping growth motivations

The research adopts a multilevel approach to study the individual-organization nexus, and joins the conversation that centers on one major strategic aspect in social enterprises: business growth. While the role of the entrepreneur and its contribution to the theory of the firm has been underestimated, studies looking at the internal determinants of small business growth suggest that if the entrepreneur has a major role in establishing the venture, this role must be equally salient in deciding whether to grow the business or not. There is a lack of understanding on how social entrepreneurs understand growth, in particular, what are the beliefs regarding the consequences of business growth for themselves and their ventures, that may be shaping social entrepreneurs' attitudes towards growth. This study aims to develop a classification scheme of expected outcomes of growth as discussed in social entrepreneurship literature. This analysis is framed using the attitude and motivation constructs from the theory of planned behavior, and therefore, the analysis focuses on business growth investigated from an individual (insider's) perspective.

Arjen van Klink, Rotterdam University of Applied Science - Business Booster: Creating Impact on SMEs through student-venturing

Most SMEs are working in the 'simple present'. They have a strong operational focus and a limited capacity in time and budget for strategy and innovation. The study wanted to find an answer to the

question: "can students play a role as catalyst for change within small and medium-sized companies?".

The bachelor students of Rotterdam University of Applied Science got the assignment to help 35 SMEs to start their 'engine for the future'. The task was to develop a business proposition as disruptive as possible, supporting one or more of the UN SDGs at the same time. The students followed the Lean Startup approach and were monitored together with the managers and entrepreneurs of the SMEs. The results of the pilot project are promising: entrepreneurs value the strategic impulse offered and students appreciate working in a reality more complex than their text books.

Lisa Gring-Pemble, George Mason University - Business for a Better World and the Honey Bee Initiative

With their Honey Bee Initiative (HBI), George Mason University embraced the imperative to respond to the decline of bee colonies and to prepare future leaders for a better world, educating students about the UN SDGs and the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. With nearly 600 hives (domestically and internationally), an established teaching and research program, thriving international programs, and dynamic public-private partnerships, HBI continues to increase its impact. It promotes multi-disciplinary, experiential, and entrepreneurial approaches to honey bee sustainability. Students from the fields of business, humanities, education, engineering, health, science and art collaborate on related problems and projects. The HBI is a huge success regarding a number of qualitative and quantitative measures of success that are built into its programs. These include institutional measures of success, changing environmental habits and behaviors, growth, health, and variety of pollinators and interviews and focus groups with the HBI stakeholders.

DAY 2: 30 OCTOBER 2019

OPENING REMARKS

On Day 2 of our Colloquium, participants were welcomed by **Tamer Boyaci, Dean of Faculty at ESMT Berlin** who highlighted ESMT's efforts in the area of sustainable development in research and education, including ESMT engagement within the ABIS network.

"AS A MEMBER OF ABIS, WE SUPPORT COLLABORATION BETWEEN BUSINESS SCHOOLS AND COMPANIES THAT ADVANCES SUSTAINABILITY EFFORTS AND CONTRIBUTES TO ACHIEVING THE UN SDGS"

OPENING REMARKS

Next, it was the turn of **ABIS CEO Ivo Matser**. In his opening remarks, he offered a reflection around the meaning of happiness, and its powerful role in personal and organizational motivation to drive action and positive impact on society.

"THERE IS NO DOUBT THAT BECOMING SUSTAINABLE IS BECOMING EVEN MORE AND MORE CRUCIAL EVERY DAY. WE NEED ACTION TO RECLAIM BEAUTY IN OUR WORLD AND FOSTER PROGRESS IN SOCIETY"

Steps on the way..

INTRODUCTORY KEYNOTE: TOWARDS A NEW PARADIGM OF BUSINESS

In her brilliant keynote speech, **Lin Lerpold, Associate Professor at Stockholm School of Economics** challenged the current "business as usual" approaches and argued in favour of a deep socio-economic system needed to tackle the complex societal challenges we are facing - climate crisis, biodiversity loss, inequality, poverty, migration. Among the others, such paradigm shift will require true corporate citizenship, long-termism and a higher degree of innovation across multiple dimensions.

"CAN BUSINESS BECOME SUSTAINABLE IN A FUNDAMENTALLY UNSUSTAINABLE BUSINESS SYSTEM?"

RENEWING THE ROLE OF BUSINESS IN CHANGING TIMES

Ryan Gellert, General Manager EMEA at Patagonia was not able to make it to the event in person, however he agreed to an exclusive interview by ABIS CEO Ivo Matser at Patagonia's European headquarters in Amsterdam. The original interview was aired for the first time at the Colloquium.

Patagonia has been recognized for years as one of the global leaders in sustainability successfully demonstrating that financial performance can and does go hand-in-hand with environmental and social performance. In the video below you can listen to Ryan explaining the reasons and drivers behind Patagonia's embodiment of sustainable and purposeful business, their new mission and their activities to support regenerative agriculture, fighting climate change and even engaging in bold political stances.

PANEL DISCUSSION: GROWING WITH POSITIVE IMPACT

Growth-at-all-cost models and the way success has been measured in our economy and business are now coming at the expense of our ability to thrive. A growing number of companies are taking steps to be more responsible in how they treat employees, customers, communities and the planet. Following the video interview with Patagonia, we invited representatives from **Accenture Strategy**, **Danone** and **Novo Nordisk**, moderated by **Mark Griffiths**, **Global Leader Climate Business Hub** at **WWF**, to share thoughts and experiences on balancing growth and positive impact and the role business is playing in addressing the SDGs.

Susanne Stormer, **VP Corporate Responsibility at Novo Nordisk**, reflected on the importance of challenging conventional thinking to support and inspire people to think differently. This is the way how progress can be made in reaching set goals, not by asking what others are doing. **Mark Griffiths** added that businesses must set a strategy and a destination even if they don't know how to get there. Businesses need to execute fast on their plan even if it means to trial and sometimes fail.

Katharina Stenholm, **SVP, Chief of Cycles and Procurement Officer at Danone**, shared that consumers are more and more interested about the origin and production of food. That is why, Danone is working to develop and promote regenerative models of agriculture that protect soil, empower farmers and promote animal welfare. Danone pledged to reduce their carbon emissions by 30 % by 2030, while Novo Nordisk managed to reach the target set with WWF on reductions in its global emissions by 10 % with their Climate Savers programme in 2014.

Alexander Holst, **Managing Director & Sustainability Strategy Practice Lead for the DACH Region at Accenture Strategy** shared that companies face a "sandwich problem" where the young talents that come to the company are motivated as well as the highest managers, but the problem arises with the

middle management. While the panellists agree on the importance to measure impact as they believe that "when it is measured, it gets managed", a challenge still seems to be the lack of data available.

The debate ended on a positive note, with a focus on how companies are working on becoming net positive. They are more and more aware that they cannot trade the negative impacts with the good things that they do and need to shift to a completely sustainable business model. The companies of the future will be those that will have an environmental and societal license to operate.

The panel session was followed by two sets of interactive breakout sessions addressing "Measuring impact" and "Creating change", that allowed participants to dive into more focused and specific topics:

- Interactive session 1.1: Measuring climate performance
- Interactive session 1.2: Impact assessment and value balancing
- Interactive session 2.1: Impactful partnership with startups
- Interactive session 2.2: Transforming business for the SDGs

INTERACTIVE SESSION 1.1: MEASURING CLIMATE PERFORMANCE

2° Investing Initiative was created in 2012 in order to help making financial regulation and investment frameworks consistent with climate goals. They developed the first science-based target setting and 2°C scenario analysis tool for financial portfolios. Their main programs for 2019 - 2022 are around enabling meaningful decarbonization plans in the financial sector, revealing retail clients' environmental objectives and introducing long-term risk supervision. **Clare Murray, Analyst at 2° Investing Initiative (2° ii)** talked about the metrics and methodologies for aligning investment portfolios with the Paris Agreement.

Clare introduced a Paris Agreement Capital Transition Assessment (PACTA) Project which is providing policymakers and financial supervisors with the tools they need to align financial flows with the Paris Agreement's goals.

Following a three-year road-testing and development phase, in September 2018, 2°ii officially launched the free, online PACTA tool with support from the UN Principles for Responsible Investment (UNPRI). The tool analyses exposure to climate-change related risks in equity and fixed-income portfolios over multiple scenarios. The analysis takes < 1 min, only requires ISIN codes and amounts, is free of charge and completely anonymous (available at <https://www.transitionmonitor.com/>).

INTERACTIVE SESSION 1.2: IMPACT ASSESSMENT AND VALUE BALANCING

Susanne Klages, Model lead at Value Balancing Alliance and Manager Sustainability Services at PwC highlighted the lack of standard for measuring and disclosing the real value companies provide to society and discussed the need of having a standardized, scalable and pragmatic model of impact measurement and valuation - which is the goal of the value balancing alliance.

The value balancing alliance is a non-profit organization founded in 2019 by eight international companies - BASF, Bosch, Deutsche Bank, SK Group, Novartis, LafargeHolcim, Philip Morris and SAP. It is endorsed by Deloitte, EY, KPMG, PwC, leading universities and other stakeholders from government, civil society and standard-setting organizations. It aims to create a standardized model for measuring and disclosing the environmental, human, social and financial value companies provide to society. With the support of OECD, World Bank, and the Directorate-General for the Environment, the outcome will be made publicly available for broad uptake and will target a widespread adoption by other companies.

INTERACTIVE SESSION 2.1: IMPACTFUL PARTNERSHIPS WITH STARTUPS

The session ran by **Ernesto Ciorra, Chief Innovability Officer of Enel** started off by showcasing on a practical math example that companies follow a dominant rule, which is hindering them to see the reality in many cases. Enel came up with a new word "innovability" which combines innovation and sustainability. The company's aim is sustainability - the survival of the company. However, a company cannot survive if it doesn't innovate. To innovate, the perspective and collaboration of outside companies - startups, resource centres and universities, is needed. These actors will only want to collaborate with a company which they consider sustainable. That is why Enel is attracting potential collaborators by being the biggest private player in renewable energy and innovating their own technologies.

Companies which would like to collaborate with Enel need to be aligned with Enel's strategic plan and priorities. Enel is gathering proposals, launching social challenges and investing in strategic planning of the best startups in their Innovation Hubs and Labs. Enel vision is holistic and is trying to act beyond an accelerator, incubator or a venture fund. Enel wants to support startups in all the important phases of their lives - from development, financing to industrialization.

concern for their business, and just **12% cite pressure from investors** as a motivation for sustainable business.

...they face a **key trade-off** in the "pressure to operate under **extreme cost-consciousness** while seeking to invest in **longer-term strategic objectives**."

Mark J. O...
CEO, East...

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INTERACTIVE SESSION 2.2: TRANSFORMING BUSINESS FOR THE SDGS

Alexander Holst, Managing Director at Accenture Strategy and Sustainability

addressed the progress and barriers that are preventing businesses from doing more to contribute to the SDGs. Alexander shared the insights from the UN Global Compact-Accenture Strategy 2019 CEO Study, the world's largest CEO study on sustainability to date.

Collaboration with business and key CEOs in the world is crucial when it comes to fighting climate change and meeting the SDGs. 40% of CEOs surveyed in 2019 said sustainability is driving revenue growth and 35% are realizing value through cost reduction today. However, CEOs themselves acknowledged that their industries and business as a whole are not doing enough. Those same leaders agree that for the majority of businesses, awareness and commitment is not driving the level of urgency and concrete action required. Leaders say market constraints and an ever more challenging business environment and set of pressures continue to slow broad-scale transition to sustainable business — and that unless broader business is forced by a shift in economic incentives, action will stall.

For the first time, leaders in 2019 are calling for their sectors and peers to step up action and course-correct the private sector contribution to the Global Goals. To accelerate progress, CEOs identify three critical requirements:

1. An urgent need to raise corporate ambition within their own organizations through 'threshold' actions and also lead systems transformation more broadly against the 17 Global Goals
2. The need for business, governments, regulators and nongovernmental organizations to come together to shape realistic science-based solutions to the global challenges
3. A new definition and emphasis on disruptive responsible leadership, as CEOs pinpoint what is needed from this generation of leaders to drive action and impact

SULAPAC

BEST IMPACT START-UP AWARD

The top 3 finalists of the ABIS Best Impact Startup Award - Resourcify, Value for Good and Sulapac were invited to the 18th Annual Colloquium to present their business activities and demonstrate their positive social, economic or environmental impact in a pitching competition. The audience, which consisted of sustainability experts from our business and academic network, civil society organization and junior enterprises awarded the best startup by online voting.

The winner of our Best Impact Startup Award is Sulapac® - a biodegradable and microplastic-free material made entirely from renewable sources and certified wood. Sulapac was acknowledged to positively contribute to sustainable development and inspiring others to do the same and was awarded a full ABIS institutional membership for a year, a private meeting with the Managing Director & Sustainability Strategy Practice Lead of Accenture, Alexander Holst and a 3D printed material prize which was handed over by Ivo Matser.

“TO FIND A WAY OUT FROM THE PLASTIC WASTE CRISIS, WE NEED TO JOIN FORCES AND GET ACTIVATED ON ALL LEVELS OF SOCIETY, ACROSS INDUSTRIES AND DISCIPLINES” MAIJA POHJAKALLIO, SUSTAINABILITY DIRECTOR, SULAPAC

PARTNERING FOR IMPACT

Following the interactive sessions, **Florian Schildheuer, President at JE Europe** and **Marco Matrisciano, Research Projects and Funding Manager at ABIS** presented the importance of collaboration for increasing impact by showcasing our new partnership. A memorandum of understanding was signed this year in June: ABIS and JEE agreed to strengthen mutual participation in each other's activities and projects and to develop new joint activities to foster sustainable development.

ABIS and JEE are combining their expertise and networks to contribute to the implementation of the UN SDGs through a multi-stakeholders partnership **training of future leaders**. We co-organize **Building Leadership for Sustainability Workshops** where junior entrepreneurs engage in scenario exploration and future-oriented systemic thinking and practice the skills needed to integrate sustainability into organizational strategies and activities. Interested to know more? You can contact marco.matrisciano@abis-global.org.

Merging the practical experience of the entrepreneurial ownership, Junior Enterprises are a relevant complement to the formal education, maximising the value for the university students.

It is about enhancing the opportunities for students to foster their knowledge and skills.

CLOSING KEYNOTE: THE INVESTOR REVOLUTION

In her closing keynote, **Ulrika Hasselgren, Global Head of Sustainability & Impact Investment at Danske Bank** offered her perspective on the role of investors in fostering a shift towards a more sustainable business practices and social and environmental value creation.

"UNLESS THE ESG DATA CHALLENGE - QUALITY OF DATA, STANDARDIZATION, TRANSPARENCY AND INFRASTRUCTURE OF DIFFERENT METHODOLOGIES - IS SOLVED, THERE WILL BE NO INVESTOR REVOLUTION"

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We would like to thank our long-term member ESMT Berlin for co-organizing and hosting our Colloquium, especially **Joanna Radeke, Manager at Center for Sustainable Business and Leadership at ESMT Berlin** for co-developing the program, her organisational support as well as the opportunity to be hosted in a fabulous location .

We would like to thank our speakers for their professionalism and their willingness to share their experiences and insights. A big thank you also to all our members that took the time to come, exchange their ideas, dive into discussions and give us feedback on our work!

WHAT PARTICIPANTS SAID:

"It was a pleasure to participate in the event and congratulations on the effort and results"

"As this was the first time at ABIS, it was a very nice experience! Great organizers and nice participants, all engaged in the area"

"A big thank you for the invitation to participate in your stimulating day yesterday! Well done in bringing together an interesting array of attendees and speakers"

"Excellent organisation with excellent sessions. I thoroughly enjoyed it!"

"We truly enjoyed the experience and hope there will be ways to collaborate with ABIS in the future!"

PHOTOS OF THE EVENT

